

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MICRO FRACTURE PROCESS OF HYBRID COMPOSITE MATERIAL WITH CF SHEETS AND MICRO GLASS BALLOON

Yoshihito Ozawa¹, Yuki Nakajima², and Takuto Omura^{2*}

¹ Faculty of Symbiotic Systems Science, Fukushima University, Fukushima, Japan

² School of Symbiotic Systems Science, Graduate School of Fukushima University, Fukushima, Japan

* s1870008@ipc.fukushima-u.ac.jp

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, as increasing aging population and declining birthrate in the developed countries, the demand of robot equipment for welfare is increasing. Therefore, high strength and low density structural materials are required to improve safety and energy efficiency. We are focusing on Shirasu Balloons (SB), a micro glassy hollow sphere shell, and have developed a hybrid composite material system. The hybrid composite material system consists of the core material of SB and epoxy resin with the CF sheet as the surface material. To improve the interfacial strength between SB and epoxy resins, the silane coupling treatment were prepared for SB before molding the core material. In this study, Three-point bending test and Acoustic Emission (AE) test were conducted to clarify and evaluate the mechanical properties and micro fracture process of cylindrical specimen of the SB hybrid material system. From the experimental results of the mechanical properties, several cracks occurred into the core composite part of the hybrid composite. We performed analysis with Finite Element Method (FEM) in order to analyse the fracture mechanism of the composite. In addition, Izod impact test was performed for cylindrical specimen of the SB hybrid material system. The impact properties was examined from the experimental results. By using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), the observations for interfacial debonding were performed in the viewpoint of micro-mechanical study.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to improve the safety and reliability of welfare equipment, reasonable weight saving is strongly required. When we developed a light structure material [1], we focused on Shirasu balloon (SB), and composed a light weight core material with SB and epoxy resin, and Carbon Fiber (CF) sheets as a surface material, that is the SB hybrid material system. SB is a micro glassy hollow spheres material which has superior lightness and heat insulation. To improve the interfacial strength between SB and epoxy resins, SB was subjected to silane coupling treatment and prepared before molding the core material.

In this report, the three-point bending test with the Acoustic Emission (AE) analysis and Izod impact test were carried out to clarify the mechanical properties of the SB hybrid material system and its microscopic fracture process. By applying FEM analysis for bending test, we examined the behavior of the material system and the progress of cracks.

2 SB COMPOSITE MATERIAL SYSTEM

2.1 SB Core Material

The matrix resin used in this study was EPOXY RESIN XNR 7425 of Nagase Chemtex Co. Ltd., bisphenol A-type epoxy resin. The hardener was HN-5500 of Hitachi Chemical Co. Ltd., hexa-

hydrophthalic anhydride hardener. The hardening accelerator was #2E4MZ of Shikoku Chemical Co. Ltd., imidazole type. SB used in this study was Maarlite 732C of Marunaka-Hakudo Co. Their average diameter of particles was about 45 μm .

The surface treatment of SB was done to reinforce interface adhesion because the interface debonding between SB and matrix was observed in the previous research. The surface treatment was conducted by using silane coupling agent, 3-aminopropyl-trimethoxysilane (APS) with wet method. APS treatment concentration was set at 1.5 wt% as following the previous research on the examination for the APS effects [2].

SB core material consists of a mixture of the resin, hardener, and SB. The resin was mixed hardener and hardening accelerator together, and the mixture was hold under vacuum environment to remove bubbles. After that, SB was mixed into the mixture together. The volume of SB is set equal to that of the mixture. In the similar way, bubbles were removed from the SB/epoxy resin mixture. The SB mixture was cured under original heat cycle. And then, the cured SB composite was separated into three layers. The three layers were SB composite layer, the matrix layer and the broken SB layer. The only SB composite layer was used for SB core material.

2.2 Hybrid Composite Material

SB hybrid composite specimens were prepared by combining Carbon Fiber reinforced plastics, TR3110GMP of Mitsubishi Rayon Co. Ltd. as a surface material with the SB core material, and the CF oriented direction of specimens was 0/90. The surface material is 3k plain weave cross ply prepreg sheet. This prepreg sheet is wound for a solid cylinder of SB core material at one turn. After that, non-extended PET sheet was wound onto the CF sheet, and was fastened with polyimide tape. It was heated in the condition of 423 K for 120 minutes for curing. The PET tape applied pressure to the material system because it contracted by heating. Then, the resin in prepreg flowed into between SB core material and CF sheet, and adhered each other.

Figure 1: The SB hybrid material system.

3 THREE-POINT BENDING TEST AND AE TEST

3.1 Three-point bending test condition

Three-point bending test was performed to clarify the mechanical properties of SB core materials and SB hybrid composites. The test specimen was 100 ± 2 mm in length, 10 ± 0.2 mm in diameter. The testing span is 64 mm, and the cross head speed was 0.1 mm/min during the test. After the bending test, the broken specimen was cut with a diamond cutter to observe the state of internal fracture on the cut surface.

3.2 AE test

The Acoustic Emission (AE) method is a method that directly detects elastic waves associated with the occurrence of defects such as cracks, and nondestructively detects and evaluates individual cracks from the number of occurrences, signal strength and their frequency characteristics [3]. The AE test

was performed to clarify the failure process occurring inside the test specimen during the three-point bending test. The AE measurement system consists of an AE sensor that detects AE waves, an amplification device that amplifies the weak AE signal, an AE measurement device "DISP", and a computer that stores data. The AE sensor used was a resonance type piezoelectric ceramic with a resonance frequency of 150 kHz with a gain of 40 dB. The geometry of sensor was 19 mm in diameter, 22 mm in thickness. Considering that the shape of the test specimen is cylindrical, the AE sensor was attached with silicon grease and an insulating tape on the adhesion surface of load element. Figure 2 shows a schematic view of the three-point bending test and AE test. The AE signal was processed by a high pass filter of 10 kHz.

Figure 2: Bending test and AE test.

3.3 Test results

Table 1 shows the results of the bending properties of SB core material and SB hybrid composite material and show the specific bending strengths, which is the bending strength divided by density, and the specific bending modulus. The specific bending modulus of SB core material was 2.92 MN·m/kg, and that of SB hybrid composite was 4.53 MN·m/kg. The CF sheets which was wound around SB core material, can improve higher specific bending strength at nearly four times and specific bending modulus at nearly one and a half times.

	SB core material	SB hybrid composite
Density [10^3kg/m^3]	0.668	0.715
Bending strength [MPa]	30.9	125
Bending modulus [GPa]	1.95	3.24
Specific bending strength [kN·m/kg]	46.2	175
Specific bending modulus [MN·m/kg]	2.92	4.53

Table 1: Mechanical properties of SB hybrid composite material and SB core material.

Figure 3 shows the mechanical behavior of bending stress against time during the bending test, and the energy value of AE signals which was obtained by multiplying AE signal amplitude and AE signal duration time. Considering the change in the bending stress of the specimen in Fig. 3, when the bending stress reaches around 70 MPa, a large stress drop observed. It means that some microfractures occurred inside the material. The change of bending stress against time with AE events shows that AE events with large energy are observed when stress drop is observed. By comparing the change of the bending stress curve with the cumulative value of the AE energy, the stress drop coincides with the

time at which the rapid increase of the AE energy occurs. From these facts, it is confirmed that a large crack is generated at the point where stress drop occurs in the bending test. Also, it is considered that the point where the AE energy is generated and rapidly increased was clearly observed, and the increasing start point can be defined as the limit point for the material in safe use. The limit bending stress of SB hybrid composite material can be seen about 70 MPa.

Figure 3: Mechanical behavior of SB hybrid composite specimen with AE events (a) and with cumulative value of AE energy (b) against time.

Figure 4 shows the cross section of broken specimen of SB hybrid composite material after bending test. Cracks were initiated and propagated to the direction of nearly 45° in the tensile part. This is considered that the specimen was subjected to shearing stress which was caused by the appearance of tensile stress in the lower side and compressive stress in the upper side. It can be also seen that some cracks initiated symmetry to the line of loading.

Figure 4: Cross section of broken specimen of SB hybrid composite for bending test.

4 NUMERICAL SIMULATION ON STRESS STATE OF SB HYBRID COMPOSITES

4.1 Numerical simulation using finite element method

Following the three-point bending test, it was found that cracks were generated in the SB core material of the SB hybrid composite material. Therefore, by conducting a numerical simulation by the use of the Finite Element Method (FEM) with an analytical model for a three-point bending test specimen, the analysis results are compared with experiments, and a more detailed evaluation of crack initiation is clarified. In this study, we used Marc and Mentat of MSC software for FEM analysis.

4.2 Analysis model and analysis conditions

In order to perform FEM analysis for bending test and impact test, each analysis model was created by the use of Mentat. The analytical model generated is shown in Fig.5 for bending test. Since a cylindrical test specimen is used for bending test, a model of the same geometry is used for FEM

analysis. The number of elements in the analysis model is 12992 for the core material part and 13440 for the surface part. An analysis model was created on the assumption that the core material and the surface material were completely bonded. The material properties of the core material are Young's modulus 1240 MPa and Poisson's ratio 0.30. Table 2 shows the material properties of the surface material of CF sheet which are used in the analysis.

In the analysis, a rigid cylinder of a jig was brought into contact with the same position as in the three-point bending test, and the boundary conditions were set and constrained so that the load point moves downward whether no displacement occurs at the the node in contact with the fulcrums. The loading jig is a cylinder with a diameter of 3 mm, and the supporting fulcrum is a cylinder with a diameter of 4 mm. By increasing load, the analytical model was deformed to a deflection of 3.5 mm at which the specimen broke, and the stress of the hybrid composite material in the longitudinal cross section was examined.

Characteristic	Unit	Value
E_1	MPa	60000
E_2		60000
E_3		8000
G_{12}		3800
G_{23}		3200
G_{31}		3200
ν_{12}		0.08
ν_{23}	0.465	
ν_{31}	0.049	

Table 2: Material characteristics of CF sheet for 0° direction.

Figure 5: FEM analysis model for three-point bending test.

4.3 Analysis result of stress state

Figure 6 shows the vector diagram of first principal stress on the core material. Viewing at Fig. 6, the direction of each vector at the nodal point of core section is parallel to the length direction of the specimen just below the load point, but the vector direction became aligned at approximately 45° away from the load point. Since the crack is considered to propagate in the direction perpendicular to this first principal stress vector, it is found that the crack generated in the part away from immediately below the load point develops in the direction of 45°. It can be thought that this inclination of cracks is affected by the shear stress in the specimen. This stress state from the analysis corresponds to the fracture surface of test specimen in figure 4. In addition, Fig. 7 shows the change of the first principal stress along the nodes on the lower side of the core material near the surface material, that is, against the distance from immediately below the load point. The first principal stress in the core part takes a maximum value about at 5 mm. Therefore, it is can be seen that the first crack under bending test occurs at the point of 5 mm away from the load point.

Figure 6: Vector diagram of first principle stress from FEM analysis result for three-point bending test.

Figure 7: Change of first principle stress against distance from loading point.

5 IZOD IMPACT TEST

5.1 Izod impact test condition

To examine the dynamic mechanical properties of the composites, Izod impact test was performed for the SB hybrid composites. For the geometry of specimens, the length of specimen was 100 ± 2 mm, and the diameter of specimen was 10 ± 0.2 mm. In the test conditions, the mass of the hammer was 80 kg, the lifted swing angle was 135° , and the impact speed was 3.46 m/s. Izod impact strength is defined as the broken energy divided by the cross-sectional area of the specimen.

5.2 Test results

Table 3 shows the impact properties of SB core material and SB hybrid composite material with no treatment, and that with APS surface treatment. In the comparison with Izod impact strength of SB core material and that of SB hybrid composite material, the specimen of SB core material with no treatment took the value of 2.23 kJ/m^2 , and the specimen of SB hybrid composite material with no treatment took the value of 17.9 kJ/m^2 . The CF sheet which was wound around the SB core material with no treatment, can also improve Izod impact strength at nearly eight times. The specimen of SB hybrid composite material with APS treatment took the value of 18.3 kJ/m^2 whether the specimen SB core material with APS treatment took the value of 1.76 kJ/m^2 . In the case of the specimen with APS surface treatment, the value of Izod impact strength can be improved nearly at ten times. It can be seen that the use of CF sheets as the surface material is expected to improve the impact properties of SB core material. Regarding the effect of the APS treatment, the impact strength of the SB hybrid composite specimen with APS treatment was almost the same as that of the non-treated specimen,

however, the Izod impact strength is not improved for the test specimen for SB core material with APS treatment. Figure 8 shows the cross section of the broken specimen of SB hybrid composite after Izod impact test. A large crack at the center and inclined cracks can be observed in the cross section of broke specimen.

	SB/E composite	SB hybrid composite
Density [10^3kg/m^3]	0.642	0.707
Cross-sectional area [mm^2]	78.5	80.1
Izod impact strength [kJ/m^2]	2.23	17.9

(a) With no surface treatment

	SB core material	SB hybrid composite
Density [10^3kg/m^3]	0.597	0.663
Cross-sectional area [mm^2]	78.5	79.9
Izod impact strength [kJ/m^2]	1.76	18.3

(b) With APS surface treatment

Table 3: Impact properties of SB core material and SB hybrid composite.

Figure 8: Cross section of the broken specimen of SB hybrid composite after Izod impact test.

The fractured surface of the test specimen after Izod impact test was observed by using SEM. In the impact test, a fractured surface was observed on the fix side opposite to the impact side. The SEM photographs of the fracture surface of the SB core material and that of the SB hybrid composite material after the Izod impact test are shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively. Referring to Fig. 9, not broken spherical SBs were observed for SB core material with no treated. Spherical SBs not broken was also observed for no treated SB hybrid composite material on Fig. 10 (a). Figure 11 schematically shows the crack expanding path. In the case of the weak interfacial debonding, cracks propegate along the SB surface and the crack expansion path becomes complicated [4]. Therefore, in the SB core material specimens with no treatment, the amount of impact energy absorption increased and the Izod impact strength is increased.

In the SB hybrid composite material, Izod impact strength was higher in SB hybrid composites with APS treatment than with no treatment. When the interfacial debonding strength increases by taking surface treatment, and the cracks propegate the SB core material along the simple straight path, and the interlaminar area of hybrid composite between the surface material and the SB core material is still strong, then, the effect of the surface material play an important role for the impact resitivity.

Figure 9: SEM photograph of the fracture surfaces of SB core material after Izod impact test.

Figure 10: SEM photograph of fracture surfaces of SB hybrid composite material after Izod impact test.

Figure 11: The crack extension pass.

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, three-point bending test with AE test and Izod impact test were performed for SB hybrid composite material. The bending properties were improved by using CF sheets wound around SB core material. The limit bending stress of SB hybrid composite material could be defined from the relationship between bending stress and accumulating AE energy.

Izod impact tests have shown that the use of CF sheets wound around a core composite improves the impact properties. According to the examination of the effect of APS treatment, the test specimens of the SB hybrid composite material with the APS treatment had higher Izod impact strength than that of with no treatment material whether the test specimens of the APS treated SB core material had lower Izod impact strength than that of the untreated one. The fracture surface were observed by SEM, and the fracture mechanism was explained by the experimental results.

The state of the first principal stress of hybrid composite material in the longitudinal cross section was examined by FEM analysis results for simulating the bending test, and it is found that the first crack is initiated at the direction of 45° to longitudinal direction. In addition, we were able to determine the location where the first crack occurred in the SB hybrid material.

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